

CREATIVITY-NURTURING SKILLS OF PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR 21ST-CENTURY CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

The primary purpose of this study is to assess the creativity-nurturing skills of Science teachers in selected public high schools in the second district of Misamis Oriental. This study used a correlational research design. Through simple random sampling, 40 respondents were chosen to gather responses using a 5-Point Likert scale with 27 items adapted from Creativity Fostering Teacher Behavior Index developed by Soh (2015). The findings indicate that most science teachers in the chosen schools were female, between the ages of 26 and 35, and had at least six to ten years of teaching experience. The findings also indicate that teachers at the selected public schools in the 2nd district of Misamis Oriental had very high levels of creativity-nurturing skill across the factors, except for independence and judgment, which were just high. Along with the findings, it was discovered that there is no significant difference in teachers' ability to nurture creativity based on age, sex, or teaching experience. Furthermore, the findings did not indicate any relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their capacity to nurture creativity. It is advised that additional research be conducted while considering a bigger sample size, and teachers from other locations are necessary to generalize the findings of this study.

INTRODUCTION

It is believed that nurturing creativity in the classroom is essential for teaching and learning. It will assist students in building their life skills and ultimately benefit the country when implemented in schools. Every teacher is encouraged to promote creativity in the classroom by the great need to develop oneself to cope with globalization and 21st-century living. Improving and nurturing creative and critical thinking skills is crucial throughout 21st-century learning (Bloom & Doss, 2019). Creativity can inspire good changes in educational methods and transform the classroom into a dynamic and active learning environment (Erin Justyna, 2016). Creativity is the ability to generate innovative and helpful or relevant ideas and things (Runco & Jaeger, 2012). The term "creative nurturing" is used in this study to describe teachers who are also creative and who nurture students as adults. Creativity-nurturing skill is the teachers' capability to be creative individuals and their ability to foster creativity in students. The teacher's creativity-nurturing skill ensures students' proficiency in the 21st-century labor market (Chan & Yuen, 2014). As the twenty-first century reaffirms, higher-order reasoning abilities should always be imparted to today's students (Osborne, 2013). The primary purpose

of this study is to assess the creativity-nurturing skills of Science teachers in selected public junior high schools in the 2nd district of Misamis Oriental. Specifically, the researchers of this study surveyed to determine the ¹demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and teaching experience, to evaluate the ²level of Science teacher’s creativity-nurturing skills, and to identify if there is a ³significant difference and ⁴significant relationship between Science teacher’s creativity-nurturing skills and their age,

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research method, explicitly utilizing a correlational research design. The respondents of this study were the 40 Junior High School Science teachers from public high schools in the 2nd district of Misamis Oriental and were chosen primarily by a simple random sampling technique. The researchers used the 5-Point Likert scale with a 27-item questionnaire as an instrument to gather information and collect data samples. The first part of the instrument contained the respondents' personal information, including their names, ages, the schools where they teach, and their years of teaching experience, and the second part of the instrument was the survey questionnaire on Creativity-nurturing skills. The tools utilized to evaluate the data were the frequency and percentage distribution, mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance, Spearman correlation, and Point-Biserial correlation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teachers’ Demographic Profile in Terms of Sex, Age, and Teaching Experience

Teachers’ Demographic Profile in Terms of Sex

Figure 1 shows the demographic profile of the Teachers in terms of sex. It reveals that 82.50% of respondents were female, and 17.50% were male. This indicates that most of the Science teachers in selected public schools in the 2nd district of Misamis Oriental were female, and only a few were male. According to the census data in the Philippines, there are more female teachers, and more women are engaged in education-related programs. According to data, only 22.94% of teachers in public secondary schools are male, compared to 77.06% of female teachers (Webmaster, 2014).

Figure 1: The Demographic Profile of the Teachers in Terms of Sex

Teachers' Demographic Profile in Terms of Age

Figure 2 shows the demographic profile of Teachers in terms of Age. It reveals that 30% were aged 26-30 years old and another 30% were 31 to 35 years old, 15 were aged 51 years old and above, 10% were aged 46-50 years old, 7.50% were aged 25 years old and below, 5% were aged 36-40 years old, and only 2.50% were 41 to 45 years old. This indicates that most Science teachers in selected public schools in the 2nd district of Misamis Oriental were 26-35 years old.

Figure 2: The Demographic Profile of the Teachers in Terms of Age

Teachers' Demographic Profile in Terms of Teaching Experience

Figure 3 shows the demographic profile of teachers in terms of Teaching Experience. It reveals that 40% had 6-10 years of experience, 27.50% had 1-5 years of experience, 10.00% had 11-15 years of experience, while only a few had 16 years and above teaching experience. This indicates that most of the Science teachers employed in selected public schools in the 2nd district of Misamis Oriental already had at least 6-10 years of teaching experience. Some are new ones with 1-5 years of teaching experience. Graham et al. (2020) discovered that there is no indication of lower teaching quality, nor how they foster creativity for new teachers, despite the fact that some of them are less experienced.

Figure 3: The Demographic Profile of the Teachers in Terms of Teaching Experience

The Level of Public High School Teachers’ Creativity-Nurturing Skills for 21st-Century Classroom Management

The results indicate that among the nine (9) factors that affect the level of creativity-nurturing teachers’ skills, the high only is in the factor of Independence (Mean=4.34, SD=0.86, Often) and Judgment (Mean=4.33, SD=0.66, Often). In contrast, the rest of the factors of creativity-nurturing skills, namely Integration (Mean=4.81, SD=0.39, Always), Motivation (Mean=4.89, SD=0.34, Always), Flexibility (Mean=4.58, SD=0.64, Always), Evaluation (Mean=4.57, SD=0.62, Always), Questions (Mean= 4.71, SD= 0.50, Always), Opportunities (Mean=4.63, SD=0.56, Always) and Frustrations (Mean=4.82, SD=0.39, Always) are very high since the respondents claimed “Always” in the factors mentioned above. The respondents claimed Always (Mean=4.63, SD=0.55), which implies that the level of creativity-nurturing skill of the teachers in the selected public schools in the 2nd district of Misamis Oriental was Very High.

The Difference between Public High School Teachers’ Creativity-Nurturing Skills and Their Age, Sex, and Teaching Experience

Table 1 shows the difference in public high school teachers’ creativity-nurturing skills based on age, sex, and teaching experience. The result reveals there is no significant difference in Creativity Nurturing Skills and demographic profile in terms of sex (F=0.984, p=0.516), Age (F=0.872, p=0.356), and Teaching Experience (F=0.182, p=0.968) since all their p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected and concludes that the Teacher’s Creativity- Nurturing Skills are the same or have no difference with respect to their age, sex, and teaching experience.

The overall results highlighted that there was not any statistically significant difference in public high school Science teachers' creativity-nurturing skills based on their age, sex, and teaching experience. This study reinforces the findings of previous studies, such as by Ken Nee Chee (2016), when he found out that there is no significant difference between male and female teachers in their creative teaching tendencies. In terms of teaching experience, this study reinforces the findings of a previous study by Kinai (2013) that there are no significant differences in creativity because of teaching experience or that creative productivity does not necessarily develop due to teaching experience.

Table 1: The Difference between public high school teachers’ creativity nurturing skills and their age, sex, and teaching experience.

Demographic	Teachers’ Creativity-Nurturing Skills		
	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Sex	0.984	0.516	Not Significant
Age	0.872	0.356	Not Significant
Teaching Experience	0.182	0.968	Not Significant

The Relationship between Public High School Teachers’ Creativity-Nurturing Skills and Their Age, Sex, and Teaching Experience

Table 2 shows the relationship between public high school teachers’ creativity-nurturing skills and their age, sex, & teaching experience using the Biserial and Spearman correlation. The figure

shows that the Creativity Nurturing Teacher Skills does not depend on age, gender, or teaching experience. The results of this study are coherent with the study of Kinai (2013), who examined Kenyan teachers' levels of creativity and their relationships with sex, age, and teaching experience. He claims that factors like age, sex, and teaching background don't really affect how creativity develops or how creativity can be nurtured. Several aspects influence it, such as diverse thinking, intellectual capacity, and training. Alphaugh and Birren (1977) also tested 111 teachers between the ages of 22 and 83 as part of a cross-cultural study on creative productivity. Their results also provided evidence in favor of the notion that creativity does not deteriorate with age.

Overall, the demographic profile of the respondents (Age: $r=0.15$, $p=0.356$; Sex: $r=-0.047$, $p=0.772$; TE: $r=-0.168$, $p=0.299$) was not significantly related to their level of creativity-nurturing skills because the overall results of their p-values are greater than 0.05. Therefore, it appears that the teachers' abilities to nurture creativity are unaffected by the demographic profile. The ability of the teachers to nurture creativity will not necessarily change if they are associated with the demographic profile. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected only in the relationship between age and level of creativity-nurturing skill in the factor of Independence.

Table 2: The Relationship between Demographic Profile and Public High School Teachers' Creativity- Nurturing Skills

Creativity-Nurturing Skills Factors	Demographic Profile								
	Sex			Age			TE		
	r-value	p-value	Remarks	r-value	p-value	Remarks	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Independence	0.15	0.356	Not Significant	-.329*	0.038	SIGNIFICANT	-0.278	0.082	Not Significant
Integration	0.136	0.402	Not Significant	0.211	0.191	Not Significant	0.1	0.541	Not Significant
Motivation	0.107	0.51	Not Significant	0.113	0.487	Not Significant	0.209	0.196	Not Significant
Judgment	-0.04	0.808	Not Significant	0.012	0.942	Not Significant	-0.108	0.508	Not Significant
Flexibility	0.214	0.184	Not Significant	0.169	0.297	Not Significant	0.055	0.737	Not Significant
Evaluation	0.046	0.78	Not Significant	0.116	0.476	Not Significant	0.007	0.968	Not Significant
Question	0.062	0.706	Not Significant	-0.007	0.965	Not Significant	-0.146	0.369	Not Significant
Opportunities	0.142	0.382	Not Significant	-0.065	0.691	Not Significant	-0.128	0.432	Not Significant
Frustration	0.115	0.478	Not Significant	-0.086	0.6	Not Significant	-0.189	0.243	Not Significant
Overall	0.15	0.356	Not Significant	-0.047	0.772	Not Significant	-0.168	0.299	Not Significant
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).									
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).									

CONCLUSION

To implement proper standards of creative scientific education in the classroom, it is thought that teachers themselves should be creative individuals. They must think creatively about running their classroom by utilizing efficient management strategies and providing relevant science material. According to this study, the respondents' demographic profile needs to indicate how well they can nurture creativity. Regardless of age or prior teaching experience, science teachers, male or female, show nearly identical levels of creativity-nurturing skills. This may be one explanation for why the study's Science instructors' cognitive growth was so comparable, as they all lived in the same area and had the same teaching experiences. It is, therefore, not surprising that they utilized nearly the same level of ingenuity to manage their class. The aggregate findings also suggest no correlation between the respondents' demographic characteristics and creativity-fostering abilities.

Hence, neither the respondents' demographic profile nor teaching experience has any bearing on or impacts their ability to foster creativity. Since science is a constant thought process, it inspires students and teachers to experiment, ask questions, and try new things. Through science, they can learn about trial and error and how experiments can succeed or fail. Teachers can also understand that they can try something again if it does not work the first time. It encourages creativity, inquiry, problem-solving, and resourcefulness, allowing them to attempt new things and fail. Science is distinctive in that it frequently begins with a question rather than a predetermined solution because solutions are rarely found in a black-and-white manner. These all contribute to the development and ongoing creativity. This may be why science teachers are expected to have high levels and be equally adept at developing creativity in students regardless of the teachers' ages, sexes, and levels of teaching experience. Science is creative in a similar way to how art, music, or literature are creative, and the same is true of science teachers.

It is advised that additional research be conducted while considering a few essential elements. Research involving a bigger sample size and teachers from other locations is necessary to generalize the findings. Future studies should consider additional factors besides the respondents' demographic profile that may significantly impact the teacher's capacity to foster creativity. Future research can also benefit from adding a qualitative study component, such as field notes from observations or in-depth teacher interviews, from supplementing the quantitative data.

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